

THE INTERPLAY OF LAW & SOCIETY

by

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ABSTRACT

Change in society necessitates a shift in the social order. Natural, social behavioural, social interactions, social organizations, and the community of people are all examples of social structures. Social change is a shift in the established social hierarchy. Social structures and cultural patterns have changed significantly throughout time, according to Charles Harper.

"Social Change" is a term which is used to describe a shift in social norms. The social and political environment is dynamic and ever-changing. Generally, social change is defined as a shift in the structure of society. Gainsberg defines social change as a shift in the social structure, such as the size, composition, or balance of a society, or the nature of the organization that makes up that society. To put it another way, Jones defines social change as a "variation or alteration" in any part of social process, social patterns, or social interaction. Social change, according to Davis, occurs when a substantial number of people participate in activities that are different from those they engaged in before. Forms or procedures themselves have to be restructured or changed, as per Anderson and Parker.

Keywords: Law, Societal Change, Society, Legal Transformation

INTRODUCTION

Law can be merely defined as a set of rules used to regulate, or rather, control, a community. A society is a diverse community of individuals from many classes, castes, creeds, colors, genders, and backgrounds. No distinction must be made between these people regardless of their identities, thereby achieving homogeneity, which the application of the law can only accomplish. Each society and its citizens look forward to social change because positive change is always welcomed. Law is critical in bringing about social change. A lawless civilization is devoid of harmony and tranquility amongst its citizens and society as a whole. As society comprises diverse individuals, there will always be a chance for one group of people to assume control and dominance over others owing to variables such as money, power, and status. This predicament is not novel; every culture has encountered it on occasion. Not only that, but society is also confronted with many other difficulties. Poverty, drug misuse, bribery, rape, murder, and discrimination based on caste, race, color, or gender are just a few examples.

Law acts as a propeller for society, removing all obstacles through enacting legislation and laws that benefit society's current and future well-being. Over the last few years, society has evolved drastically. While legislation has been instrumental in bringing about these changes, it is essential to remember that societal challenges are not disappearing; on the contrary, they are speeding. It is time for society to employ existing laws efficiently to bring about meaningful social transformation effectively. The law is essential to a community because it creates a set of rules for everyone to follow. It was also designed to establish proper norms and order for all people's behaviour and ensure that the three branches of the government are equal. It is the lifeblood of society. When there are no laws, chaos reigns, this is not, for the most part, a desirable way of life. The law is significant because it establishes a foundation for what is socially acceptable. Without it, conflicts between social groupings and communities would erupt. We must follow them. The law is adaptable to changes in society (Harper, 1993).

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LAW AND SOCIETY

The legal system reflects the vitality of any civilization. Law possesses the sophisticated energy of a living entity. Rules are never created nor used in a vacuum; instead, they are created and applied repeatedly for a specific purpose. Rules are meant to either propel us in a path we

believe is beneficial or to prevent us from moving in a direction we believe is detrimental. The society's members establish societal rules. Disobedience of the laws of society is followed by social disapproval as punishment. There is no positive sanction for rule violations other than ex-communication or ostracism. On either hand, the state is responsible for enforcing the law. The law aims to bring order to society so that people can grow and develop while feeling secure about their future. The state enacts legislation. Defiance of state laws carries a penalty that is imposed by the government using the state's power. What is unenforceable does not constitute law (Fox, 1991).

Law influences politics, economics, and society in various ways and acts as a societal mediator in interpersonal relationships. Criminal law provides a method for the state to prosecute the wrongdoer if the act of injury is criminalized. Constitutional law establishes a framework for enacting legislation, safeguarding human rights, and electing political representatives. Administrative law examines government agency decisions, whereas international law oversees interactions between sovereign governments in various areas, from trade to environmental legislation and military action. The legal response to a particular social or technological challenge is thus a significant social action in and of itself, capable of aggravating or alleviating the situation and assisting in its resolution (Cummings, 2013).

THE RULE OF LAW AS A MEANS OF SOCIAL CONTROL

The first of the law's dual purposes is to preserve the status quo and ensure that people may live their lives in an orderly fashion in the community. Second, to influence social change by adapting oneself to the requirements of an ever-evolving society in order to better the influence of such change. Therefore, the law is a significant component of the system that maintains social order. In the sake of greater socialization, the society prioritizes itself above the law. The primacy of the rule of law in a democratic nation's governing document is essential. The public is kept in check by the use of social control mechanisms such as the law, which creates fear in people. The behaviour of individuals in society is controlled by the legal system. The people are made aware of their responsibilities and obligations through use of force by the legal system. The rule of law protects the most important and admirable ideals of society. The rule of law puts a stop to the exploitation of the public at large. This objective is baked into India's constitutional framework, as well as the nation's criminal and civil laws, as well as other regulations.

LAW- IDEAL TOOL FOR SOCIAL CHANGE AND SOCIAL TRANSFORMATION

SOCIAL CHANGE:

It is important to comprehend the workings of the legal system in the light of political, social, and economic viewpoints, all of which can be found in the constitution of India, in order to have an understanding of the societal change that has occurred as a result of laws and the legal system. The law is a reflection of how people relate to each other, their values, and what they believe to be valued in life, as well as how individuals define their own feeling of safety and security. It is also a reflection of how the people see the world and what they believe to be important.

There have been various societal issues that the law has addressed and attempted to change. Justice PN Bhagwati once stated that judges are responsible for infusing life and blood into a legislative structure to build a living element capable of meeting the requirements of society. Without the assistance of legislators, legislation as a concept cannot control or affect social change. Thus, one method in which law can be used to effect social change is through the judges who have been law holders. Society is confronted with some social obstacles that have stymied global progress (Mohan, 2009). Major societal duties, which hinder the law from being carried to the grassroots and used as a tool for social change are given below:

1. **RACIAL DISCRIMINATION**- Racial bias is a societal problem that has plagued numerous countries worldwide for centuries. Racial discrimination occurs when two groups of individuals are treated unequally based on their skin color or ethnic origin. As most Americans have stated, the globe still has a long way to eliminate racial discrimination, and statistics confirm this. Parts of America, Africa, and India have long suffered from severe racial persecution. Racism fosters inequality in society, which is unjust and unjustifiable. Numerous countries have enacted anti-discrimination legislation to eradicate racial discrimination as well.

2. **CLIMATE CHANGE**- Climate change is a recent addition to this squad. Climate change is a pressing issue since it affects the entire population in several ways. Numerous great leaders have stated that handling changing climate as a social problem will require increased public participation to raise awareness of the dire consequences. Typhoons have already begun to strike various locations of the South Pacific as a result of climate change. The earth is gradually

losing its biodiversity as a result of this problem. Conventions, dialogues, and treaties are being held to prevent this societal problem from escalating. Applying the law through treaties, acts, and conventions demonstrate that law is a tool for social change.

3. **EXPLOITATION OF WOMEN AND CHILDREN**- Exploitation of children and women has long been a global social issue. This is an example of a societal issue that does indeed adhere to the cyclic hypothesis. Historically women have been oppressed as a result of men assuming authority over them. This has also resulted in an increase in crimes against women in comparison to men. Child labor, child maltreatment, child marriage, and child trafficking are all examples of child exploitation. Numerous laws have been enacted to regulate these elements to effect social change and to protect children's rights to provide them with an atmosphere in which they can develop into responsible members of the nation. Through *Vishakha vs. State of Rajasthan*¹, the SC commissioned the Vishakha guidelines, which defined sexual harassment and placed the burden of providing a safe workplace environment for women squarely on employers.

The social concerns described above are considered some of the most severe social problems facing the globe today, and it is only through the law that change can be brought about in society.

SOCIAL TRANSFORMATION:

The following are some of the societal developments brought by the application of law as a tool:

1. **PUBLIC INTEREST LITIGATION**- Public interest litigation is one such instrument that the Supreme Court has endowed individuals with to foster a different approach to law on their side. It is a mechanism by which an individual representing a group of individuals can approach the court on the grounds that they are harmed by something that must be prohibited in order to avert further suffering. By providing citizens with public interest litigation, the SC has been able to narrow the scope of the locus standi, allowing any public-spirited individual to contact the court without reservation.

¹ *Vishakha vs. State of Rajasthan*, AIR, SC 3011, [1997]

This was a significant social transformation brought about by the Indian court, demonstrating once again that legislation may be used as a tool to effect social change in the manner desired by society. In a handful of instances, public interest litigation has had a significant impact on society. Among these is the *M.C. Mehta vs. Union of India*² case. In this public interest case, the Supreme Court was requested to provide people with a free and healthy environment in water, air, and the surrounding environment. It was determined that these demands fell within reach of Article 21³ of the Indian Constitution.

2. **RAPE**- Rape is more than a societal issue resulting from the national mindset. Instead of defining it according to who does it and who suffers, rape can be described as sexual exploitation of an individual by another person for the latter's gratification. Only via legislation could there be a shift in the psyche of persons in society, causing them to abstain from such horrible acts. India has observed a dramatic increase in rape incidents among females, indicating that before educating our society's daughters, it is vital to educate the majority of our population. By instilling terror in offenders, societal change can be affected by instilling dread in them and compelling them to think twice before committing any act of this nature. Only after the Nirbhaya case, the 2013 amendment act was established.

3. **LGBTQIA+**: Section 377⁴ of the Indian Penal Code, 1860, which used to criminalize unnatural acts such as intercourse between two men or two women, was repealed by the SC of India on the basis that homosexuality is no longer a crime under the law. In the historic ruling *Navtej Singh Johar vs. Union of India*⁵, the Supreme Court decriminalized all the forms of consensual sex between adults, including sex between individuals of the same gender. This Supreme Court ruling ushered in a sea change in Indian society, traditions, and beliefs. It was a resounding victory for the vast majority of the people, particularly the LGBTQ community. The Supreme Court effectively reaffirmed Article 21 by stating that every individual has a right to life liberty that community norms should not restrict.

4. **CHILD MARRIAGE**- India, which is home to many different faiths, has a rich cultural heritage that includes a variety of values and cultures that have been codified into legislation

² *M.C.Mehta vs. Union of India*, AIR 1086, [1987]

³ Article 21 of Indian Constitution- Protection of life and personal liberty

⁴ Section 377 of Indian Penal Code- Unnatural offences

⁵ *Navtej Singh Johar vs. Union of India*, 10 SCC 1 [2018], 3

<http://www.sconline.com.eu1.proxy.openathens.net/DocumentLink/M077VWho>

over the course of many years, despite the fact that some of these customs and traditions were not morally sound or equitable. One of these unethical rituals that used to be widespread before the Child Marriage Restraint Act of 1929⁶ was passed was the practice of marrying children. This Act went through further amendments in the year 2006 and became known as the Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006⁷ as a result of those changes. The exploitation of young women through the practice of child marriage is one method. At an age when youngsters should be pursuing an education, they are getting married in order to free their parents and society from the duties of caring for them. The youngster will suffer a great deal as a consequence of the same. Because, the society was in need of the same thing, the use of legal force was essential in order to get rid of this social problem that was plaguing society. In order to bring about the desired transformation in society, legislation was enacted and made mandatory for everyone to comply with.

5. FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS OF THE INDIAN CONSTITUTION:

The idea that the law may be used as a tool to effect fundamental societal shifts is reflected in the concept of fundamental rights. Fundamental rights include the right to equality under Article 14⁸, the right to freedom under Article 19⁹, the right to live freely under Article 21¹⁰, the right to receive a free and compulsory education under Article 21, and several other rights that prove to be essential to make a difference in the society. The fundamental rights are enforceable in the court of law, which means that individuals have the right to petition the court if they believe that their fundamental rights have been violated in any way. In the year 2002, Article 21A of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was updated to include a new provision called the "right to free and compulsory education"¹¹. The society recognized the need of providing its children with an education in order to raise their level of sensitivity to the social transformation that was going on all around them. The passage of legislation was the chosen method for achieving the desired result, which was to ensure that all children up to the age of 14 were required to attend school.

⁶ The Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929, Act 19, Acts of Parliament (1929)

⁷ CHILD MARRIAGE ACT, 2006. ACT NO. 6 OF 2007, Act of Parliament (2006)

⁸ Article 14, The Constitution of India, 1950

⁹ Article 19, The Constitution of India, 1950

¹⁰ Article 21, The Constitution of India, 1950

¹¹ Article 21A, 86th Amendment Act, 2002, The Constitution of India, 1950

In the case of *Beru Bari*¹², which took place in 1969, the Supreme Court of India came to the conclusion that the preamble is not a component of the constitution; hence, parliament does not have the jurisdiction to amend it. In the end, the Supreme Court ruled in the case of *Kesavananda Bharati vs the State of Kerala* (1973)¹³ that reading the preamble as a part of the constitution is not in error.

6. **ABOLITION OF SATI SYSTEM:** It is called "Sati," which means burning or burying the widow's body together with her husband's. Since ancient times, being a sati has been regarded as a tremendous honour among Hindus. In 1812, Indian social reformer Raja Ram Mohan Roy launched a campaign against these abuses. Societies could not prohibit this practice since it was seen as part of their cultural heritage. In 1829, the legislation was in place that could govern it. Sati, the burning or burial of Hindu widows, was declared unlawful and punished by criminal courts by Governor Lord William Bentick in Bengal presidency areas by an order. Sati remained unchecked in post-independence India. Under the Commission of Sati Act, 1987, anybody who aids or abets sati is subject to a penalty of up to death, which the legislature regarded seriously. It is now a relic of the past in many parts of India. In response to public outcry, certain regulations were created governing sati, widow remarriage, and child marriage. Sociological jurisprudence did not apply to the colonial administration's legislation. Various social reformers and the general public piqued their interest in these bills.

7. **WIDOWS REMARRIAGE:** In Hindu tradition, remarriage of widows was frowned upon in order to protect the reputation and wealth of their deceased husband's family. Because of Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar's efforts, the British government passed a statute that allowed Hindu women to remarry when a previous marriage ended in divorce or death. As a direct consequence of this, the Hindu Widow Remarriage Act¹⁴ was passed into law in the year 1856. Providing Hindu widows with the ability to remarry while at the same time offering legal safeguards against the loss of certain forms of inherited property should they want to do so is the goal of this legislation. A Hindu widow was thus provided all the resources necessary to lead a typical life.¹⁵

¹² *The Berubari Union vs Unknown*, AIR 1960 SC 845

¹³ *Kesavananda Bharati vs the State of Kerala*, AIR 1973 SC 1461

¹⁴ *The Hindu Widows Re-Marriage Act, 1856*. Act XV of 1856, (1856)

¹⁵ Priyadeep Mahapatra, *Law as An Instrument of Social Change* (May. 25, 2022), <https://aishwaryasandeep.com/2021/06/27/law-as-an-instrument-of-social-change/>

CONCLUSION

When looking at social issues from the systems viewpoint, one must understand that they are not isolated but rather interrelated. People need to support strong opinions that can be supported on psychological and political grounds, in conformity with fundamental concepts such as justice, dignity and equality.

So, it can be concluded that law does change society, but there are several loopholes also. Rape laws have been enacted. But the number of rapes has not decreased. Every other day, a rape event would be reported in the newspaper. This demonstrates unequivocally that the existing laws are insufficient to effect social transformation. The world continues to endure racial and caste discrimination. Protests, mass rallies, and everything else is faltering because the rules currently in place lack the necessary roots to have a social influence. While homosexuality has been mainstreamed, few embrace it because it violates social norms. As a result, it is vital to address these societal concerns through strengthened law enforcement to consider laws carefully and attentively. Thus, it may be claimed that law is already a tool for bringing about social change; indeed, it has brought about a great deal of social change; but it still has a long road ahead to go before bringing about a societal revolution.

